

**COMPARATIVE SIXER SHOT STUDY BETWEEN ANTEGRADE AND RETROGRADE
PERISTALSIS UMPIRING BY ACTION POTENTIAL**

Dr. Dhrubo Jyoti Sen, Rishikesh Chatterjee* and Bhagyasri Debnath

School of Pharmacy, Techno India University, Salt Lake City, Sector-V, EM-4/1, Kolkata-700091, West Bengal, India.

***Corresponding Author: Rishikesh Chatterjee**

School of Pharmacy, Techno India University, Salt Lake City, Sector-V, EM-4/1, Kolkata-700091, West Bengal, India. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19553900>

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ABSTRACT

Viscera of human body is concerned with mouth to stomach which is physiological support of upper half and intestine to rectum is associated with lower part so upper part comes under vomiting and lower part of GIT is associated with bowel clearance. Action potential is an electrical discharge by PQRST the five phase graphical plot inside the cell by sodium influx and potassium efflux to control over the biological wave function towards vomiting center to cause emesis by mouth in upward direction through GIT and bowel evacuation through rectum by downstream direction. In both cases peristalsis action follows antegrade as well retrograde direction to give comfort of body homeostatic physiological behavior. The vomiting out from the gut and stool clearance from anus gives a relief and satisfaction which is followed by peristalsis action through wave that is fully under control by action potential. The electrical discharge through ion channel distributed throughout the body is controlled by polarization of Na^+/K^+ influx/efflux in cellular level. The movement of a cell's membrane potential to a more positive value is referred to as depolarization. The change in membrane potential from a positive to a negative value is referred to as repolarization. Depolarization is caused by a rapid rise in membrane potential opening of sodium channels in the cellular membrane, resulting in a large influx of sodium ions. Membrane Repolarization results from rapid sodium channel inactivation as well as a large efflux of potassium ions resulting from activated potassium channels. Action potentials conduct with a finite velocity along nerve axons, and the actual velocity depends on a number of factors that include: fibre radius, temperature, functional ion channel number and the presence of a myelin sheath.

KEYWORDS: depolarization, overshoot, repolarization, hyperpolarization, refractory period, PQRST plot, CTZ, vomiting, bowel clearance, chime, antegrade peristalsis, retrograde peristalsis.

INTRODUCTION

An action potential is a rapid sequence of changes in the voltage across a membrane. The membrane voltage, or potential, is determined at any time by the relative ratio of ions, extracellular to intracellular, and the permeability of each ion. An action potential can be further broken down into its separate stages: **depolarization, repolarization, hyperpolarization**, and the **refractory period**. An action potential is defined as a sudden, fast, transitory, and propagating change of the resting membrane potential. Only neurons and muscle cells are capable of generating an action potential; that

property is called the excitability. For example, when we smell a scent, the olfactory neurons in the nose fire action potentials as a response. Thus, action potentials are the result of a stimulus. Action potentials are triggered by a stimulus which results in a shift of the ion concentrations in and out of the cell.^[1]

Action potentials (those electrical impulses that send signals around your body) are nothing more than a temporary shift (from negative to positive) in the neuron's membrane potential caused by ions suddenly flowing in and out of the neuron.

Figure-1: Action Potential & Electrical Charges.

The course of the action potential can be divided into five parts: **the rising phase [depolarization], the peak phase [overshoot], the falling phase [repolarization], the undershoot phase [hyperpolarization], and the refractory period [PQRST plot]**. During the rising phase the membrane potential depolarizes (becomes more positive). The action potential has three main stages: depolarization, repolarization, and hyperpolarization. It is called the action potential because the positive charge then flows through the

cytoplasm, activating sodium channels along the entire length of the nerve fiber. The action potential, also referred to as a nerve impulse, is the electrical potential difference across the plasma membrane. Action potentials are of great importance to the functioning of the brain since they propagate information in the nervous system to the central nervous system and propagate commands initiated in the central nervous system to the periphery.^[2]

Figure-2: PQRST plot with axon electrical discharge.

Pharmacology: Action Potential Characteristics Can Change: The voltage-gated ion channels are located along the axon hillock and axon; they open in response to the membrane potential reaching a threshold value. The rising phase of the action potential is a result of sodium influx. **Depolarization:** loss of polarization. Especially loss of the difference in charge between the inside and outside of the plasma membrane of a muscle or nerve cell due to a change in permeability and migration of sodium ions to the interior. **Repolarization:** The movement of a cell's membrane potential to a more positive value is referred to as depolarization. The change in membrane potential from a positive to a negative value is referred to as repolarization.^[3] Depolarization is caused by a rapid rise in membrane

potential opening of sodium channels in the cellular membrane, resulting in a large influx of sodium ions. Membrane Repolarization results from rapid sodium channel inactivation as well as a large efflux of potassium ions resulting from activated potassium channels. Action potentials conduct with a finite velocity along nerve axons, and the actual velocity depends on a number of factors that include: fibre radius, temperature, functional ion channel number and the presence of a myelin sheath. The physical basis of conduction is explained by the local circuit hypothesis. Depolarization is when a change occurs inside a cell that causes the distribution of electric charges to alter, leaving the cell with a less negative charge than the outside. Numerous cell functions, cell-cell communication, and the general

physiology of an organism all depend on depolarization. Action potentials are caused when different ions cross the neuron membrane.^[4]

A stimulus first causes sodium channels to open. Because there are many more sodium ions on the outside, and the inside of the neuron is negative relative to the outside, sodium ions rush into the neuron. An action potential is a rapid sequence of changes in the voltage across a membrane. The membrane voltage, or potential, is determined at any time by the relative ratio of ions, extracellular to intracellular, and the permeability of each ion. A stimulus is applied at time = 1 ms, which raises the membrane potential above -55

mV (the threshold potential). After the stimulus is applied, the membrane potential rapidly rises to a peak potential of +40 mV at time = 2 ms. The membrane potential will reach +30 mV by the time sodium has entered the cell. As the membrane potential reaches +30 mV, other voltage-gated channels are opening in the membrane.^[5]

When two pulses meet, they reveal information about their physical nature. Upon running into each other, two action potentials in an excitable plant cell annihilate - Action potentials in plant cells and nerves are similar nonlinear phenomena.^[7]

Figure-3: Cross Section of Nerve Tissue.

Luigi Galvani [9 September 1737 – 4 December 1798] was an Italian physician, physicist, biologist and

philosopher, who studied animal electricity took the first step by demonstrating the presence of electricity in

animal tissues. Over the next half-century, others went on to show that nerve and muscle tissues generate electrical transients that accompany excitation, but the lack of sensitive instruments hampered these studies. Axon diameter, internode distance, and myelin sheath thickness all influence the speed of action potential propagation. Moreover, these factors are to a certain degree correlated with each other. The Action Potential. The movement of a signal through the neuron and its

axon is all about ions. An ion is a charged particle, such as Na^+ , the sodium ion.^[8] It has a positive charge, because it is missing one electron. This mechanism of action potential generation represents a positive feedback loop: Activating the voltage-dependent Na^+ conductance increases Na^+ entry into the neuron, which makes the membrane potential depolarize, which leads to the activation of still more Na^+ conductance, more Na^+ entry, and still further.

Figure-4: Luigi Galvani; the founder of ion channel by Action Potential.

At the junction between two neurons (synapse), an action potential causes neuron A to release a chemical neurotransmitter. The neurotransmitter can either help (excite) or hinder (inhibit) neuron B from firing its own action potential. From this work arose the hypothesis, now well established for many neuron types that the action potential normally initiates in the axon initial segment. It is one way. But action potentials move in one direction. This is achieved because the sodium channels have a refractory period following activation, during which they cannot open again. This ensures that the action potential is propagated in a specific direction along the axon.^[9]

Emesis: The chemoreceptor trigger zone (CTZ) is an area of the medulla oblongata that receives inputs from blood-borne drugs or hormones, and communicates with other structures in the vomiting center to initiate vomiting. The CTZ is located within the area postrema, which is on the floor of the fourth ventricle and is outside of the blood-brain barrier. It is also part of the vomiting center itself. The neurotransmitters implicated in the control of nausea and vomiting include acetylcholine, dopamine, histamine (H1 receptor), substance P (NK-1 receptor), and serotonin (5-HT₃ receptor). There are also opioid receptors present, which may be involved in the mechanism by which opiates cause nausea and vomiting.

The blood–brain barrier is not as developed here; therefore, drugs such as dopamine which cannot normally enter the CNS may still stimulate the CTZ.^[10] The chemoreceptor trigger zone (CTZ) is an area of the medulla oblongata that receives inputs from blood-borne

drugs or hormones, and communicates with other structures in the vomiting center to initiate vomiting. Within the CTZ, opioid stimulation at the mu receptor induces emesis, while on mu receptors within the BBB, specifically the NTS, stimulation inhibits emesis.

Figure-5: Chemoreceptor Trigger Zone.

The tenth cranial nerve or the vagus nerve carries signals to the CTZ when the back of the throat or pharynx is irritated or stimulated. This is called the gag reflex. The nervous system around the gut or the enteric nervous system also transmits signals to the brain via the vagus nerve.^[11] Peristalsis is the involuntary contraction and relaxation of longitudinal and circular muscles throughout the digestive tract, allowing for the propulsion of contents beginning in the pharynx and ending in the anus. A series of normal coordinated, rhythmic muscle contractions that occurs automatically to move food through the digestive tract is called peristalsis. The peristaltic movement, also known as peristalsis, is the contraction and relaxation of the oesophagus and the food pipe, which causes the food to be pushed down the track to the stomach. This involuntary movement is required to transport food

through the stomach and bowels through the anus. Peristalsis is the automatic wave-like movement of the muscles that line your gastrointestinal tract.^[12]

Peristalsis moves food through your digestive system, beginning in your throat when you swallow and continuing through your esophagus, stomach and intestines while you digest. Peristalsis and segmentation are fundamentally different from one another since segmentation refers to the rhythmic contractions of the circular muscles in the digestive system. In contrast, peristalsis refers to the contractile activity of the longitudinal muscles in the gastrointestinal tract. Peristaltic contractions, in addition to influx from the small intestine, facilitate movement of ingesta through the colon.^[13]

Figure-6: Peristaltic wave.

Mass movements constitute a type of motility not seen

elsewhere in the digestive tube.

3 functions of peristalsis: [1] Peristalsis created by the muscle contraction facilitates food movement downwards via the esophagus to the stomach. [2] Peristalsis propels the food downwards in the bolus form. The stomach converts the food into chyme form. [3] Peristalsis also facilitates the movement of chyme towards the small intestine. Chyme is the semi-fluid mass of partly digested food that is expelled by a person's or an animal's stomach, through the pyloric valve, into the duodenum (the beginning of the small intestine). Chyme results from the mechanical and chemical breakdown of a bolus and consists of partially digested food, water, hydrochloric acid, and various digestive enzymes. Chyme slowly passes through the pyloric sphincter and into the duodenum, where the extraction of nutrients begins. Depending on the quantity and contents of the meal, the stomach will digest the food into chyme in some time from 40 minutes to 3 hours. [Peristalsis is a manifestation of two major reflexes within the enteric nervous system that are stimulated by a bolus of foodstuff in the lumen. Mechanical distension and perhaps mucosal irritation stimulate afferent enteric neurons.^[14] Intestinal peristalsis is regulated by the

enteric nervous system and is influenced by dietary and microbial changes. The rippling motion of muscles in the intestine or other tubular organs characterized by the alternate contraction and relaxation of the muscles that propel the contents onward. Because of the reliance of the peristaltic reflex on the myenteric plexus, it is also referred to as the myenteric reflex. Peristalsis can be defined as a motor pattern of the gut organ musculature that can propel content into the anal (antegrade peristalsis) or oral (retrograde peristalsis) direction. Antegrade Peristalsis [anal route]: The recurring contraction and relaxation of muscles is termed as peristalsis. In the oesophagus, three types of peristalsis occurs as follows: Primary esophageal peristalsis, Secondary esophageal peristalsis, Tertiary esophageal peristalsis. It is noticed in the alimentary canal and uterine canal. Peristalsis is generally directed caudal, that is, towards the anus. This sense of direction might be attributable to the polarization of the myenteric plexus. Because of the reliance of the peristaltic reflex on the myenteric plexus, it is also referred to as the myenteric reflex.^[15]

Figure-7: Emesis pharmacology.

Peristalsis occurs in the alimentary canal by gastrin and the peristalsis of the uterine walls occurs by oxytocin and estrogen. When the wave-like muscle contractions of peristalsis move backward instead of forward, it's called retroperistalsis, antiperistalsis or reverse peristalsis. This is what happens when your vomiting reflex is triggered. The key difference between peristalsis and antiperistalsis is the direction of food movements. Peristalsis pushes downwards while antiperistalsis, which is reverse, pushes upwards. Peristalsis, involuntary movements of the longitudinal and circular muscles, primarily in the digestive tract but occasionally in other hollow tubes of the body, that occur in progressive wavelike contractions. Peristalsis pushes the food downward in one direction while segmentation does not cause for net movement of food inside the GI tract. This is the key difference between peristalsis and segmentation. Digestion and absorption are regulated by the different types of muscular movements of the gastrointestinal

system. *Muscularis propria* (externa): smooth muscle layer. These layers of smooth muscle are used for peristalsis (rhythmic waves of contraction), to move food down through the gut.^[16]

Two types of motor activity have been recognized: segmenting contractions and peristaltic contractions. The predominant motor action of the small intestine is the segmenting contraction, which is a localized circumferential contraction, principally of the circular muscle of the intestinal wall. Retro peristalsis is the reverse of the involuntary smooth muscle contractions of peristalsis. It usually occurs as a precursor to vomiting. Local irritation of the stomach, such as bacteria or food poisoning, activates the emetic center of the brain which in turn signals an imminent vomiting reflex.^[17] Retroperistalsis is the reverse of the involuntary smooth muscle contractions of peristalsis. It usually occurs as a precursor to vomiting. Local irritation of the stomach,

such as bacteria or food poisoning, activates the emetic center of the brain which in turn signals an imminent vomiting reflex. Retro peristalsis begins in the small intestine and pyloric sphincter. Food then moves in the opposite direction, often from the duodenum into the stomach. Retro peristalsis occurs pathologically during vomiting and physiologically at the first part of the duodenum where it protects from high acidity of food, and also at the terminal ileum, where an amount of water and electrolytes are absorbed to assist defecation. Evacuation of GIT by two ways: vomiting [upward

direction] and bowel passing [downward direction]. The entire system is controlled by two ways: CTZ in upward direction for vomiting and rectal clearance by downward direction. Belching is commonly known as burping. It's your body's way of expelling excess air from your upper digestive tract. Most belching is caused by swallowing excess air. This air most often never even reaches the stomach but accumulates in the esophagus. In bowl evacuation either in normal state as well as in loose motion state all are followed by action potential.

Figure-8: GIT and bowel clearance.

CONCLUSION

Our body viscera has two openings: mouth for vomiting and rectum for stool evacuation. Both the evacuation mechanism is controlled by action potential. Vomiting/Emesis cause upwards. The action potential as expressed by Hodgkin and Huxley (1952) is a measurement of the progression of ionic charge over the axon membrane, but it cannot represent the mechanism of propagation. The peak amplitude of the action potential is 75 mV and the total duration 400 ms. All these action potentials are recorded in response to an

intracellular depolarizing pulse or to the stimulation of afferents. Note the differences in their durations. This passive current flow depolarizes the membrane potential in the adjacent region of the axon, thus opening the Na^+ channels in the neighboring membrane. The local depolarization triggers an action potential in this region, which then spreads again in a continuing cycle until the end of the axon is reached. The resting potential is the state of the membrane at a voltage of -70 mV, so the sodium cation entering the cell will cause it to become less negative. This is known as depolarization, meaning

the membrane potential moves toward zero. After depolarizations are abnormal depolarizations of cardiac myocytes that interrupt phase 2, phase 3, or phase 4 of the cardiac action potential in the electrical conduction system of the heart. After depolarizations may lead to cardiac arrhythmias. Repolarization refers to the change in membrane potential that returns it to a negative value just after the depolarization phase of an action potential has changed the membrane potential to a positive value. Primary function as repolarization reserve is to prevent spontaneous delayed after depolarization during Phase 4 of the action potential. In physiology, repolarization is the process or act of restoring the polarized condition across the plasma membrane of a cell, e.g. nerve cell. During the normal resting state, the membrane potential is a negative value. The opening of channels that let positive ions flow into the cell can cause depolarization. Example: Opening of channels that let Na⁺ start text, N, a, end text, start superscript, plus, end superscript into the cell. Because the wave of depolarization is moving toward the positive electrode, by convention, a positive voltage (upward deflection) is recorded. The voltage reaches its maximal positive value when half the tissue is depolarized. Depolarization occurs in the four chambers of the heart: both atria first, and then both ventricles. The sinoatrial (SA) node on the wall of the right atrium initiates depolarization in the right and left atria, causing contraction, which corresponds to the P wave on an electrocardiogram.

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